

ANALYSIS OF BASIC FUTSAL TECHNICAL SKILLS FROM INDONESIAN NATIONAL TEAM PLAYERS IN THE TOURNAMENT AFF FUTSAL CHAMPIONSHIP

АНАЛІЗ ОСНОВНИХ ФУТЗАЛЬНИХ ТЕХНІЧНИХ УМІНЬ ІНДОНЕЗІЙСЬКИХ ГРАВЦІВ НАЦІОНАЛЬНИХ КОМАНД У ТУРНІРІ АФФ З ФУТЗАЛЬНОГО ЧЕМПІОНАТУ

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze basic futsal technical skills of Indonesian national team players in the AFF Championship tournament. This type of research in this research is descriptive research. Researchers observed through recording and calculating the competition for the success of basic futsal technical skills for the Indonesian National Team players, the basic technical needs for futsal games from the Indonesian National Futsal Team, and the dominant technical elements carried out by the Indonesian National Futsal team players to exercise control of the ball. The sample used is all Indonesian National Team Players in the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament, totaling 14 players. Sampling using total sampling method. The table format of Match Analysis is used by the author to analyze the match as a data collection instrument. The analysis technique used in this research is descriptive statistical analysis. By counting the number of passing, dribbling, shooting and controlling techniques for the Indonesian National Futsal Team Players in the AFF Championship Tournament. From the results of the basic technical analysis of futsal games for Indonesian Futsal National Team players at the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament, it can be concluded that the statistical average of the 3 matches that have been run by the Indonesian futsal team for passing techniques has a total number of 909 where the correct passing is 793 (87%) and for incorrect passes 116 (12%). The total number of Dribbling techniques is 182 where for correct dribbling amounted to 120 (66%) while incorrect dribbling is 62 (34%). Control technique has a total number of 691 where the correct control technique is 645 (93%) and for the wrong control technique 46 (7%). The total number of shooting techniques was 91, where the correct shots amounted to 72 (79%) while the wrong ones were 62 (21%).

Key words: Skills Analysis, Basic Futsal Techniques, AFF Futsal Championship.

Це дослідження має на меті проаналізувати основні технічні навички футзальних гравців збірної Індонезії на турнірі чемпіонату АФФ (Азійської футбольної федерації). Цей тип дослідження в цій статті є описовим. Дослідники оглянули через фіксацію та розрахунки змагання на успіх базових технічних навичок з футзалу для гравців збірної Індонезії, основні технічні потреби у футзальних іграх збірної Індонезії з міні-футболу та домінуючі технічні елементи, які виконують гравці національної збірної Індонезії з футзалу для здійснення контролю над м'ячем. Для прикладу використано усіх гравців національної збірної Індонезії на турнірі чемпіонату АФФ з футзалу, загалом 14 гравців. Вибірка проводилася методом загальної вибірки. Формат таблиці аналізу відповідності використовується авторами для аналізу відповідності як інструменту збору даних. Метод аналізу, використаний у цьому дослідженні, – описовий статистичний аналіз. Підраховували кількість передач, дриблінгу, ударів та технік контролю для гравців національної команди Індонезії з футзалу на турнірі чемпіонату АФФ. З результатів базового технічного аналізу футзальних ігор для гравців збірної Індонезії з міні-футболу на турнірі Чемпіонату АФФ з футзалу можна зробити висновок, що середнє статистичне значення 3 матчів, проведених командою Індонезії з футзалу з техніки передачі, має загальну кількість 909, де правильний прохід – 793 (87%), а неправильні – 116 (12%). Загальна кількість методів дриблінгу становить 182, де правильний дриблінг склав 120 (66%), тоді як неправильний дриблінг – 62 (34%). Загальна кількість технік контролю – 691, де правильна техніка контролю – 645 (93%), а неправильних технік контролю – 46 (7%). Загальна кількість ударних технік склала 91, де правильні постріли склали 72 (79%), а неправильні – 62 (21%).

Ключові слова: аналіз навичок, основні техніки футзалу, чемпіонат АФФ з футзалу.

Introduction. Futsal is a team game similar to football played on a small field, and the size of the ball used is also smaller (Hadi, 2019). Each team is played by five players and accompanied by reserve players (Susi, 2016).

To score as many goals as possible against the opponent's goal is the goal of the futsal game (Hanafi & Christina Yuli Hartati, 2015). The team that is able to score more goals (Sulistiantoro, 2016). The team will be the winner (Sugiarto et al., 2020).

Compared to football, futsal has more ball possession (Prastyo et al., 2017). To be able to achieve team achievements in futsal games, basic techniques must be mastered by players (Iqbal et al., 2019). Football and futsal games have basic technical similarities that can be used in matches and training (Mailani, 2016). Every futsal player must master all basic techniques such as heading or heading, shooting, passing the ball, kicking the ball, dribbling and controlling the ball (Asshagab et al., 2020). In addition to basic techniques, precise timing and the movement of players without the ball must be trained as well (Wibowo et al., 2019). Because it will help players defend and attack in a game tactic that requires high speed and this is known as modern futsal (Festiawan, 2020).

In the futsal game, mastery of basic techniques is needed by players (Rasyd et al., 2019). Players must have mentality, tactics, and physicality as important factors in improving basic abilities (Hutomo et al., 2019). So that basic skill training must be carried out and it is important to pay attention to the above factors during training in facing official competitions (Nurchahya et al., 2020). The development of significant skills in futsal is influenced by good and appropriate mastery of basic skills (Polidoro et al., 2013). Heading, shooting, controlling, dribbling, and passing are basic technical skills in futsal (Zhukova et al., 2018). Researchers carried out this research to investigate the basic technical abilities of the futsal game by the Indonesian

National Team in the AFF Competition. The video recording of the match was analyzed through the method of observation by the author in obtaining the desired data. The basic abilities of futsal players can be improved and developed is the hope of researchers in carrying out this research.

Methods. This type of research in this research is descriptive research. Researchers observed the Indonesian National Futsal Team players who faced opposing teams through match recordings. Then observe and calculate the success of the basic Futsal technical skills of the Indonesian National Team players, the basic technical needs of the futsal game from the Indonesian National Futsal Team, and the dominant technical elements carried out by the Indonesian National Futsal team players to exercise control of the ball.

The sample used is all Indonesian National Team Players in the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament, totaling 14 players. Sampling using total sampling method. The table format of Match Analysis is used by the author to analyze the match as a data collection instrument. The analysis technique used in this research is descriptive statistical analysis. By calculating the number of passing, dribbling, shooting and controlling techniques for the Indonesian National Futsal Team Players at the AFF Championship Tournament, here's how to analyze the data obtained:

1. Finding the average (mean)

$$\frac{\sum X_i}{n}$$

Information :

Me : average

$\sum X_i$: the amount of each data

n : amount of data

2. Percentage

$$\text{Percentage } X = \frac{n}{N} \times 100\%$$

N

Information :

n : number of techniques

N : total technique count

Results. Based on the results of data analysis on passing, dribbling, control, and shooting techniques obtained from the results of

3 matches of the Indonesian futsal team, it can be further described as follows:

1. Characteristics of the Passing Technique

The following are the results of the passing matches against Australia, Vietnam and carried out by the Indonesian futsal team in 3 Malaysia

Table 1. Characteristics of Passing Techniques

Number	Opponent Match	Passing		amount	Percentage	
		Right	Wrong		Right	Wrong
1	Australia	335	41	376	89,0957%	10,90425532%
2	Vietnam	271	29	300	90,3333%	9,666666667%
3	Malaysia	187	46	233	80,2575%	19,74248927%
Total		793	116	909	87,2387%	12,76127613%

From the table above, the results of the calculation of the characteristics of the passing technique can be described as follows:

- a. In the first futsal match against Australia, the Indonesian Futsal team passed 376 times, with 335 descriptions (89%) true and 41 times false (11%).
- b. In the second match with Vietnam as its opponent, the Indonesian futsal team did 300 passing activities, 271 times (90%) correct and 29 times (10%) wrong.
- c. Furthermore, in the third match the Indonesian futsal team faced Malaysia, where they carried out a total of 233

passes with 187 times (80%) correct and 46 times (20%) wrong.

- d. The total number of passing technical activities in the 3 matches of the Indonesian futsal team is a total of 909 passing techniques with 793 correct passes (87%) and 116 incorrect passing techniques (13%).
2. Characteristics of the Dribbling Technique
The following are the results of the dribbling carried out by the Indonesian futsal team in 3 matches against Australia, Vietnam and Malaysia

Table 2. Characteristics of the Dribbling Technique

Number	Opponent Match	Passing		amount	Percentage	
		Right	Wrong		Right	Wrong
1	Australia	49	27	76	64,4737%	35,52631579%
2	Vietnam	36	20	56	64,2857%	35,71428571%
3	Malaysia	35	15	50	70%	30%
Total		120	62	182	65,9341%	34,06593407%

From table 2, the results of the calculation of the characteristics of the dribbling technique can be described as follows:

- a. In the first futsal match against Australia, the Indonesian Futsal team did 76 Dribbling activities, with 49 times (64%) true and 27 false (36%) descriptions.
- b. In the second match with Vietnam as its opponent, the Indonesian futsal team did 56 Dribbling activities, 36 times (64%) were correct and 20 times (36%) were wrong.
- c. Furthermore, in the third match the Indonesian futsal team faced Malaysia, where they performed 50 total Dribbling

activities with 35 times (70%) correct and 15 times (30%) wrong.

- d. The total amount of Dribbling technique activities in 3 Indonesian futsal team matches is a total of 182 Dribbling techniques performed with each correct Dribbling technique 120 times (66%) and incorrect Dribbling technique 62 times (34%)
3. Characteristics of Control Techniques
The following are the results of the control techniques carried out by the Indonesian futsal team in 3 matches against Australia, Vietnam and Malaysia

Table 3. Characteristics of Control Techniques

Number	Opponent Match	Passing		amount	Percentage	
		Right	Wrong		Right	Wrong
1	Australia	280	12	292	95,8904	4,109589041
2	Vietnam	226	22	248	91,129	8,870967742
3	Malaysia	139	12	151	92,053	7,947019868
Total		645	46	691	93,343	6,657018813

From table 3, it can be explained that the results of the calculation of the control engineering characteristics are as follows:

- a. In the first futsal match against Australia, the Indonesia Futsal team carried out control technique activities 292 times, with descriptions of 280 times (96%) true and 12 times false (4%).
- b. In the second match with Vietnam as its opponent, the Indonesian futsal team carried out control technique activities 248 times, with 226 times (91%) correct and 22 (9%) false descriptions.
- c. Furthermore, in the third match the Indonesian futsal team faced Malaysia,

where they carried out technical control activities a total of 151 times with 139 times (93%) correct and 12 times (7%) wrong.

- d. The total control technique activity in the 3 Indonesian futsal team matches is that the total control technique was performed 691 times with each control technique being correct 645 times (93%) and performing the wrong control technique 46 times (34%).
4. Shooting Technique Characteristics
- The following are the results of the shooting techniques carried out by the Indonesian futsal team in 3 matches against Australia, Vietnam and Malaysia.

Table 4. Characteristics of Shooting Techniques

Number	Opponent Match	Passing		amount	Percentage	
		Right	Wrong		Right	Wrong
1	Australia	27	3	30	90	10
2	Vietnam	14	6	20	70	30
3	Malaysia	31	10	41	75,6098	24,3902439
Total		72	19	91	79,1209	20,87912088

From table 4, the results of the calculation of the characteristics of the shooting technique can be described as follows:

- a. In the first futsal match against Australia, the Indonesian Futsal team carried out shooting technique activities 30 times, with 27 times (90%) true and 3 false (10%) descriptions.
- b. In the second match with Vietnam as its opponent, the Indonesian futsal team did 20 shooting techniques, with 14 (70%) correct and wrong 6 times (30%) descriptions.
- c. Furthermore, in the third match the Indonesian futsal team faced Malaysia, where they carried out a total shooting

technique activity 41 times with 31 times (76%) true and 10 times (24%) wrong.

- d. The total shooting technique activity in the 3 matches of the Indonesian futsal team is a total shooting technique performed 91 times with 72 correct passes (79%) each and 19 wrong shooting techniques (21%).

Discussion. To be able to play futsal well, a player must be equipped with good basic skills or techniques, not only being able to kick the ball but also having expertise in controlling or controlling the ball. So that the basic technical skills of each player are needed in a futsal game or match. It can be concluded from the above opinion that the mastery of basic technical skills

playing futsal is very important and needed by every player, because with good basic technical skills, the game in training or competition can run optimally.

The characteristics of the mastery of basic futsal technical skills for each team in a match or competition are very different and varied. This is because every futsal team has the skills to play with different styles, advantages and disadvantages. Therefore, during the process of achieving an achievement in a match in a futsal tournament, each team is expected to be able to find out the abilities of the opponents who will be faced in the match and also measure the abilities they have before the match is held. In this way we can take preparatory steps that must be taken in facing matches in a Tournament or futsal competition.

In accordance with the formulation of the problem, research objectives and research results on the basic technical characteristics of the Indonesian Futsal National Team futsal game in the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament which was measured as many as 3 matches. In 3 futsal matches, the Indonesian national team against Australia, Vietnam and Malaysia where the data was taken from the average in 3 matches. The Indonesian futsal team tends to dominate the basic passing techniques, namely with a 48% percentage followed by basic futsal control, dribbling and shooting techniques, respectively 37%, 10%, and 5%. So, for the largest percentage in 3 matches the Indonesian futsal team dominates the basic techniques of passing.

The match time in the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament is 2x20 minutes. In one game the activities carried out include basic passing techniques, basic dribbling techniques, basic control techniques and basic shooting techniques. Based on the overall match analysis for the basic technical needs of the Indonesian National Futsal Team players, it can be seen from the total average of each technique in one match, which is as follows:

a. The passing characteristics of futsal games in 3 AFF Futsal Championship Tournament matches are as follows: total passing 909 times, 793 correct passes (87.2%) and 116 incorrect passes (12.7%). The average passing of each match was 303 times with 264.3 correct pass descriptions and 38.6

incorrect passes. So, it can be said that the characteristics of the passing techniques carried out in the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament match are mostly done correctly.

b. The passing characteristics of the futsal game in the 3 AFF Futsal Championship Tournament matches are as follows: 182 total dribbling, 120 correct dribbling (65.9%) and incorrect dribbling 62 times (34.06%). The average passing of each match was 60.6 times with 40 correct dribbling and 20.6 incorrect dribbling. So, it can be said that the characteristics of the dribbling technique performed in the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament matches are mostly done correctly.

c. The passing characteristics of the futsal game in the 3 AFF Futsal Championship Tournament matches are as follows: 691 total controls performed, 645 correct controls (93.3%) and 46 incorrect controls (6.6%). The average control performed in each match was 230.3 times with correct control descriptions 215 times and incorrect control 15.3 times. So, it can be said that the characteristics of the Control technique carried out in the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament match are mostly done correctly.

The shooting characteristics of futsal games in 3 AFF Futsal Championship Tournament matches are as follows: total shooting was taken 91 times, shooting correctly 72 times (79.1%) and shooting incorrectly 19 times (20.8%). The average shooting performed in each match was 30.3 times with 24 correct shooting descriptions and 6.3 incorrect shooting times. So, it can be said that the characteristics of the shooting technique carried out in the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament match are mostly done correctly.

Conclusion. From the results of the basic technical analysis of futsal games for Indonesian Futsal National Team players at the AFF Futsal Championship Tournament, it can be concluded that the statistical average of the 3 matches that have been run by the Indonesian futsal team for passing techniques has a total number of 909 where the correct passing is 793 (87%) for incorrect passes 116 (12%). The total number of Dribbling techniques is 182 where for correct dribbling amounted to 120 (66%) while incorrect dribbling is 62 (34%). Control

technique has a total number of 691 where the correct control technique is 645 (93%) and for the wrong control technique 46 (7%). The total

number of shooting techniques was 91, where the correct shots amounted to 72 (79%) while the wrong ones were 62 (21%).

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